

BUILDING ENTREPRENEURIAL CHARACTER IN SCHOOLS: PREPARING THE YOUNG GENERATION FOR THE WORLD OF WORK

Yul Amri^{1*}, Afliah Monalisa²

¹Universitas Dharmas Indonesia, Dharmasraya, Sumatra Barat, Indonesia

²Lembaga Pendidikan dan Pengembangan Profesi Indonesia, Indonesia

* Corresponding Author. E-mail: yulamri1065@gmail.com

Abstract

The entrepreneurial spirit emerges through a long process, especially for those who do not have experience or are not used to being in an environment that supports the growth of the entrepreneurial spirit. Often educational institutions only produce students who are skilled but do not have an entrepreneurial spirit, so that in the end students are formed as workers ready to work, not job creators. Long before, in the process of cultivating an entrepreneurial spirit through education, there was a process of forming an entrepreneurial spirit, namely through a process of learning and habituating oneself as the originator of character in the future. However, if it is related to the needs, hopes, and support of the government for the growth of the entrepreneurial spirit through education, then this matter deserves more attention. The following describes several entrepreneurial activity programs that management can carry out to foster an entrepreneurial spirit for students, namely through entrepreneurship-based extracurricular activities, field trip activities at traditional markets and MSMEs, and holding Bazar at school.

Keywords: entrepreneurial character, entrepreneurship program, young generation

INTRODUCTION

Education has a central role in shaping the future of the younger generation. Education requires media in learning. Learning media makes students able to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes (Putri et al., 2022; Arpan & Sadikin, 2020; Supardi et al., 2023; Feladi et al., 2017). Meanwhile, education is essentially inherent and exists in human life itself (Dewi, 2018). Then, one of the functions of education is to shape students' attitudes and orientation toward learning, instill a positive attitude and thirst for knowledge, and develop effective learning skills (Amar et al., 2016; Sulistiyarini et al., 2018; Batubara, 2023; Arpan et al., 2022).

However, in facing an ever-changing and competitive world of work, education should not only provide academic knowledge but also

instill entrepreneurial character. Building this character not only impacts students' chances of becoming entrepreneurs but also provides a solid foundation for success in various situations in the world of work.

The importance of creativity and innovation in entrepreneurship places it at the center of attention in modern education. The most prominent 21st-century competencies found in international frameworks that have been proven to offer measurable benefits in various areas of life are associated with critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, and innovation (Dewi et al., 2021). School should not only be a place of learning but also an environment that stimulates the imagination. In the classroom, teachers can encourage students to think creatively through problem-based projects,

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creating opportunities for them to face challenges and develop innovative solutions.

Recognizing that creativity is not something that can be taught directly, but rather is instilled through a supportive learning atmosphere, teachers must create conditions where students feel comfortable to put forward new ideas without fear of being judged or wrong. Steps like these help students understand that innovative solutions are often the key to success in various contexts (Qiu et al., 2023; Lesmana et al., 2019; Kreiterling, 2023; Diawati et al., 2023; Karlsson et al., 2021; Hardini et al., 2024).

Entrepreneurship is not only about individuals but also about the ability to work together in teams. Entrepreneurs are those who can utilize the resources that exist within themselves and in the environment around them so that they have commercial value and generate profits through the innovations they develop (Dewi et al., 2018). Schools can form these skills through various activities.

Extracurricular programs, such as student clubs or organizations, provide opportunities for students to participate in group projects and hone their communication skills. Through collaboration, students learn about team dynamics, conflict management, and the importance of cooperation. It is important to remember that developing communication skills does not only involve the speaking aspect but also the ability to listen well. Success in the world of work often depends on the ability to understand other people's perspectives and work effectively in teams. Therefore, schools should pay special attention to the development of these two aspects.

To foster an entrepreneurial spirit, it is necessary to instill an entrepreneurial mindset in students which is useful for maintaining enthusiasm and fostering a more goal-directed mind. Mindset is a belief within a person to make efforts or something that is permanent and cannot be changed (Dewi et al., 2020). One of the hallmarks of entrepreneurship is the ability to identify problems and find effective solutions. In schools, this approach can be applied through projects that challenge students to solve real problems. By providing challenges like this, schools allow students to experience how the entrepreneurial thought process works.

The teacher's role here is as a facilitator who guides students through the problem-solving process. It's not just a matter of finding the right answer, but also teaching students to look at problems from different points of view and look for innovative solutions. Learning from failure is also important in honing students' entrepreneurial character. Equipping students with entrepreneurial knowledge and skills can be done through subjects that are integrated into the curriculum. This program can cover aspects of business, business planning, and risk management. Students will get a first-hand look at the world of business, opening their minds to what is involved in managing and running a business.

Entrepreneurship training in the curriculum is to provide students with a real picture of the business world. It also helps ease the fear of uncertainty often associated with entrepreneurial steps. With the knowledge and skills gained from this training, students can feel more confident and ready to face the world of work. The dynamics of the world of work require that education providers be able to face and anticipate changes that occur by utilizing various available resources to create creative, innovative, and adaptive learning situations to create competent graduates (Dewi, 2018).

Responsibility and resilience are core values in entrepreneurial character. Schools can help shape students' character by instilling these values through a character education approach. In this curriculum, students are taught the importance of work ethics, integrity, and the ability to persevere in the face of obstacles.

METHOD

This research used descriptive qualitative methods. Methodologically, research and development have four levels, namely: 1) Research and Development at Level 1 (the lowest level) is research for produce design but does not proceed with making the product or testing it, 2) Research and Development at Level 2, where researchers do not conduct research, but directly test existing products, 3) Research and Development at Level 3, where researchers research to develop (revise) existing products, making revised products and testing the effectiveness of these products, 4) Research and Development at Level 4 is research to create new

products and test the effectiveness of these products (Sugiyono, 2016).

Qualitative research is research that emphasizes observing phenomena and requires sharp researcher instincts. Qualitative research usually studies the relationship or interaction between several study variables to understand the event being studied and generally examines case studies based on certain theories. Researchers prefer a qualitative descriptive research design because they want to describe the conditions that will be observed in the field more specifically, clearly, and in-depth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Entrepreneurship-based extracurriculars

Extracurriculars are special educational activities outside of class hours and school counseling services to help develop student's potential according to their needs, interests, and talents through creative activities specifically organized by teaching staff who have the ability and authority at the school (Nurdiana, 2021). The objectives of extracurricular activities according to the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 62 of 2014 concerning Extracurricular Activities paragraph (2) are: Extracurricular Activities are organized to develop students' potential, talents, interests, abilities, personality, cooperation and independence optimally to support the achievement of national education goals. Therefore, it is necessary to form extracurricular activities that focus on entrepreneurship, which will increase interest and instill an entrepreneurial mindset.

In entrepreneurship extracurricular activities, student activities can be filled with role-play activities, simulations, observing the school environment, and others where the aim is to train imagination, find a way out of a problem, foster motivation, build a positive spirit, cultivate a creative attitude, discipline, likes to save, charity, caring attitude and so on through various activities carried out. For this extracurricular activity to provide maximum benefits to students, the creativity of supervisors or trainers for these extracurricular entrepreneurship activities is needed as well as structured training materials so that the core

delivery of extracurricular activities can be applied by students in their daily lives.

From the results of these extracurricular observations, students are slowly starting to experience improvement, with these extracurriculars students absorb the knowledge provided by educators in these extracurriculars, starting from making simple general journals, setting prices, and developing products, as well as leadership skills that are embedded in the entrepreneurial mindset.

Conduct field trips to traditional markets and MSMEs

By holding a field trip, it is hoped that students will learn more about the world of entrepreneurial work, how to work, how to manage finances, determine prices, and provide a kind of essay sheet that will train students' thinking patterns and hone their analysis to observe and think. The benefit of this activity is that students can see it directly and connect it with the theory they have studied previously. A visit to these two different places (traditional market and modern market) can also foster their imagination and creativity, for example by provoking questions about where the real owner of the goods sold in the modern market? or mentioning what are the different things between the traditional market and the modern market. modern, and so on.

The material presented or discussed can be adjusted to the class level. After the field trip, the teachers will assess the results of the student's ideas, which will later be taken into consideration as to how many students understand the world of work and the aspects of entrepreneurship.

Set up a bazaar at school

School bazaar is usually an interesting activity for students, teachers, and parents. This trains students to develop creative, innovative products. The implementation of entrepreneurial values, namely: independent, creative, brave to take risks with action-oriented considerations, leadership, hard work, honesty, discipline, innovation, responsibility, cooperation, never giving up (tenacious), commitment, realistic, passion knowledgeable, communicative, and strong motivation to succeed. With this activity, usually, students will compete in calculating the amount of their income, and later the school will

give rewards to groups that have higher incomes compared to other groups (Indah, 2017). With the presence of the school bazaar this aim, students can apply entrepreneurship knowledge in the world of work and everyday life.

Discussion

Based on the data obtained, students experienced an increase in enthusiasm for entrepreneurship. Students who take part in extracurricular programs, field trips, and bazaar, are more capable of creativity, innovation, and leadership spirit. They begin to get used to recording their daily financial purchases and solving problems, and some even start selling at school to practice their entrepreneurial skills. So it can be found that the three activities above are able to improve mindset, interest, and train entrepreneurial skills.

This is a good result because it introduces them to the real world of work. In fostering an entrepreneurial spirit in Indonesian society, the government supports this through various schemes and programs to facilitate groups of young people to take part in the world of business and enterprise. One of the government's efforts to encourage the emergence of new entrepreneurs in the country includes the National Entrepreneurship Movement (GKN) which consists of a package for growing new entrepreneurs including training and providing initial capital as a “start-up”.

This is a step for teachers to group their students with enthusiasm for entrepreneurship so that later it will be submitted to the government for consideration in growing new entrepreneurs and expanding employment opportunities in the future.

CONCLUSION

Students can develop an entrepreneurial spirit, namely by instilling good character such as being creative, independent, able to solve problems, never giving up, able to manage money, and also being able to interact with many people. Even though there are many obstacles faced, these obstacles will not be significant. Because it can be resolved by the school. Developing entrepreneurial character

involves providing an understanding that failure is not the end of everything, but can be a stepping stone to achieving greater success. Mentorship from entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial professionals can also have a significant positive impact in guiding students to develop entrepreneurial character. Through interactions with those who have experience in the business world, students can hear success stories but also understand the challenges they may face. Building entrepreneurial character in schools is a long-term investment that will provide benefits for students not only in the world of work but also in everyday life. By teaching students to think creatively, communicate effectively, solve problems, and have responsibility, schools provide solid provisions to face the complexity and uncertainty of the future. School is not only a place where students gain knowledge, but also a stage where their character is formed and carved to become future pioneers.

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